

OPTIMIZE THE PROCESS PARAMETERS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF FUNCTIONAL EXTRUDED PRODUCT

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Abstract:

Extrusion is the process of forcing a mixture of components through a tiny aperture known as a die to create and shape objects (Launay and Lisch, 1983). Maize, soy, wheat, sorghum, and other food components are pushed to flow under pressure through multiple steps in the food extrusion manufacturing process. The extrusion process-driven extruded product was created and analyzed for integrated quality (physical characteristics, textural, nutritional, and sensory). Extruder and process combinations using rice flour (54.80 g), sorghum flour (32.88 g), guar gum powder (5.48 g), feed moisture content (6.84 g), barrel temperature (130 °C) and screw speed (350 rpm) demonstrated comparative superiority. The optimization was carried out using Design Expert software. The said optimum extrusion process combinations lead to expansion ratio 3.58, bulk density 0.05 g/cm³, hardness 890.66 g and overall acceptability 7.63. The optimized extruded product demonstrates overall nutritional quality, as moisture content, fat, protein, crude fiber, ash, carbohydrate and dietary fiber were found to be 4.56%, 0.14%, 7.80%, 3.73%, 1.06%, 82.69% and 18.29%, respectively.

Keywords: Extrusion, sorghum, guar gum, dietary fiber

Introduction:

Extrusion has its roots in the metallurgical business, where Joseph Bramah invented the first method in 1797. This technique was involved using a piston-driven tool to create seamless lead pipes. The research conducted by the plastics industry was significantly responsible for the current understanding of extrusion technology and the advancements or improvements in machine design. This technique had been in use in the food sector since 1930, and because of its sustainability, continuity, and efficiency, its popularity is growing. Sausage extruders were initially created as basic shaping devices in the nineteenth century. The usage of a pasta press known as a "cold extruder" in the middle of the 1930s was one of the early innovations that set the groundwork for the food extrusion industry. Additionally, the first time a single screw extruder was utilized to produce ready-to-eat (RTE) cereals was in the late 1930s by General Mills, Incorporation, located in Minneapolis, Minnesota, USA. Twin screw extruders were utilized later in the 1970s to produce wet pet food. Numerous modifications to the extruder's design have been observed throughout the years, including adjustments to the screw and barrel designs as well as the materials utilized in their production. In addition to segmented screws that are currently on the market, barrel liners might improve process economics and equipment longevity. Stainless steel, satellite welded steel, bimetallic HIP (Hot Isostatic Press), corrosion and wear-resistant surface-coated steels, and standard nitride steel are just a few of the materials that are being used as screw elements for improved wearing characteristics for customized processing needs (Singh *et al.* 2017). The basic principle of extrusion process is combination of transport processes, including flow of materials within the virtually controlled environment system, thermal energy transfer to and within the material, and mass transfer to and within the material during extrusion. Food ingredients of various types may be processed by extrusion and are referred to as extrudate.

Guar gum is an important source of soluble dietary fiber known as gallactomannan having high water retention capacity and can be used as a functional ingredient to avoid syneresis and to modify the viscosity and texture of some formulated foods also it acts as a bulk forming laxative and as such claimed to be effective in promoting regular bowel movements, relief constipation and chronic functional bowel ailments. It is also cheap and ideal for snack food as it prevents moisture migration. There is a global trend towards development of healthy snacks/ products and incorporation of cereals and pulses in traditional extruded products may represent a strategy for value addition of these products (Kundu *et al.* 2014). Extruded product consumption seemed to be on the rise, necessitating technical advancement through the development of new goods. The composite extruded product Puffed has been well received by customers of all ages. Because they are lower

in protein, crude fiber, vitamins, and minerals, and higher in carbohydrates, the extruded meals that are now available have a fairly poor nutritional profile. This ultimately sets off the requirement for enrichment. The extruded product's protein, dietary fiber contents are improved by the addition of sorghum and guar gum powder. The purpose of developing the extruded product was to improve the product's external look and nutritional content. The likely and futuristic extruded product gap research work for improved appealing physical features and leading one step ahead towards smart nutrition should be achieved (Athawale *et al.* 2022).

Materials and methods**Raw materials**

The present study involves preparation of extruded product by use of sorghum, guar gum powder and rice as a base material. Rice (*Cv. Gurjari*) will be procured locally from Palanpur, Gujarat and will be sieved, and cleaned. Prior to extrusion, rice will be milled to rice flour and again it will be sieved to maintain the uniformity of particle size of rice flour which will be helped in better extrusion process. Sorghum (*Cv. GJ 43*) will be procured from Sorghum Research Station, SDAU, Deesa, Gujarat and will be sieved, and cleaned. Prior to extrusion of product sorghum will be milled to sorghum flour and again it will be sieved to maintain the uniformity in particle size of rice flour. Good quality guar gum powder will be procured locally from Palanpur, Gujarat. All the above raw materials will be well packed in LDPE bags and kept in cool place prior to experiments.

Extrusion cooking

The extrusion conditions were established using machine limitations and preliminary testing. A twin screw volumetric gravity feeder was utilized to supply the pre-conditioned feed material to the twin screw extruder at a consistent pace. The feeding zone, transition zone and extrusion zone were the three heating zones in the extruder barrel. The temperature of the extrusion zone was adjusted in accordance with the experimental design, while the heater for the feeding and transition zones was left off at all times. In order to examine its impact on the finished product, screw speed was also adjusted. The die or exit had an interior diameter of 3 mm and was shaped like a cylinder (Plate 1.1). The extruded product was collected in crates. Fig. 1.1 illustrates the method used for extrusion cooking in each experiment. It also shows the extruder under processing conditions and the resultant extruded material

Plate 1.1: Die used for twin screw extruder

Fig 1.1: Flow chart of extrusion processing

Pre-treatment of feed material

To make the basic mixture for the extruded product raw ingredients such as rice flour, sorghum flour and guar gum powder were used. Since rice flour was considered a set amount, guar gum powder and sorghum flour was added to it in percentage form as per the experimental design. All of the raw ingredients were weighed using different formulas. The mixture was twice sieved to remove any potential foreign or gritty particles and it was made sure that all the components were well combined. Distilled water was added to the mixture in predetermined amount in compliance with the experimental design. The feed mixture was sieved again and left to acclimatize for one hour at room temperature in order to remove the lumps that had formed from the addition of water.

Extruded product

Following 30 min. of operation to stabilize the designated temperatures, samples were fed into the feed hopper @ 4 kg/h for a straightforward and choke-free operation. The manufacturer advised using a die diameter of 3 mm for this product. The product was collected at the end of the die.

Post treatment of extruded sample

The extruded samples were dried in a tray drier at 60 °C for 1 hour, cooled to ambient temperature and then sealed in Al/LDPE bags for storage.

Result and discussion

Rice and sorghum flour were used as cereal and millet sources for the production of an extruded product (Plate 1.2), which included guar gum powder. Rice and sorghum flour were pulverized as described in material and methods guar gum powder was incorporated as per design. The ingredients were blended according to the combinations provided by the Design Expert software. Rice flour used in fixed quantity, while sorghum flour and guar gum powder were added in the proportion of pre cent to rice flour. Independent variables were changed i.e., sorghum flour, guar gum powder, feed moisture content and machine parameters such as barrel temperature. All of which had an influence on bulk density, expansion ratio and hardness. Table 1.1 shows the impact of independent factors on the responses.

Plate 1.2: Developed extruded product

Optimization of extrusion process

According to the requirements, the following response model was chosen to describe the variety of responses for further investigation. The numerical optimization approach of the program Design Expert - version 12.0.3.0, Stat-ease, 2019 (Trial version) as stated in 3.6 of Chapter 3, was utilised for simultaneous optimization of the various replies. The Design Expert program was used to compute the optimal

mix of sorghum flour, guar gum powder, moisture content and barrel temperature. These computations yielded an extruded product of high quality with optimal values for the answers indicated and explained above. The intended goals for each component and response were selected and various weights were applied to each goal to change the form of its specific desirability function, as shown in Table 1.2

Table 1.2: The intended goals for independent variables and their responses

Factor/responses	Goal	Lower limit	Upper limit	Importance
A: Sorghum flour (%)	In range	55	65	3
B: Guar gum powder (%)	In range	10	20	3
C: Moisture content (%)	In range	12.5	17.5	3
D: Extruder barrel temperature (°C)	In range	110	130	3
Expansion ratio	Maximize	2.73	3.9	3
Bulk density (g/cm³)	Minimize	0.08	0.39	3
Hardness (g)	Minimize	746.36	1553.45	3

Predicated values of optimized sorghum based dietary fiber enriched extrudate were 59.65 % (= 60 %) sorghum flour, 10 % guar gum powder having 12.50% moisture content and keeping 130 °C barrel

temperature resulting in 3.693 expansion ratio, 0.106 g/cm³ bulk density and 925.198 g hardness with desirability of 0.837. Values of optimized parameter are mentioned in Table 1.3

Table 1.1: Effect of different flour, moisture content and extrusion temperature on extruded product quality parameter

Run	Sorghum flour (%)	Guar gum powder (%)	Moisture (%)	Temperature (°C)	Expansion ratio	Bulk density (g/cm ³)	Hardness (g)
1	55	10	12.5	110	3.17	0.32	1355.63
2	60	15	15	120	3.68	0.24	1178.52
3	55	10	17.5	110	3.10	0.34	1375.23
4	60	15	15	140	3.90	0.08	746.36
5	60	25	15	120	3.53	0.29	1283.32
6	70	15	15	120	3.50	0.26	1155.89
7	60	15	15	120	3.43	0.24	1195.21
8	60	15	15	100	2.73	0.39	1553.45
9	60	15	20	120	3.30	0.27	1125.78
10	60	15	15	120	3.42	0.23	1152.15
11	55	20	12.5	110	3.22	0.35	1475.65
12	55	10	17.5	130	3.55	0.15	873.12
13	55	20	12.5	130	3.67	0.13	1076.55
14	65	10	17.5	130	3.58	0.18	870.36
15	60	15	15	120	3.44	0.22	1150.23
16	60	15	15	120	3.46	0.25	1171.75
17	60	5	15	120	3.27	0.21	1087.94
18	65	20	17.5	110	3.12	0.36	1382.85
19	65	10	12.5	110	3.19	0.33	1445.36
20	55	20	17.5	110	3.05	0.35	1373.23
21	65	20	12.5	130	3.69	0.14	1055.52
22	65	10	17.5	110	2.97	0.35	1328.53
23	65	20	12.5	110	3.25	0.37	1405.23
24	50	15	15	120	3.37	0.20	1342.03
25	65	10	12.5	130	3.65	0.10	945.56
26	65	20	17.5	130	3.59	0.19	938.23
27	60	15	15	120	3.47	0.23	1125.23
28	55	20	17.5	130	3.56	0.17	926.14
29	55	10	12.5	130	3.63	0.11	922.23

30	60	15	10	120	3.72	0.21	1225.64
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Table 1.3: Optimization criteria for process parameters and their responses

Optimized independent variables	Values
Sorghum flour (%)	59.65 (= 60)
Guar gum powder (%)	10
Moisture content (%)	12.5
Extruder barrel temperature (°C)	130
Dependent variables	
Expansion ratio	3.693
Bulk density (g/cm ³)	0.106
Hardness (g)	924.198
Particular	
Desirability	0.837

Conclusion:

The performance of model was verified and tested by conducting experiments for the validation. For optimizing the treatment combination, practically available variables used were i.e., 54.80 g rice flour as base, 32.88 g sorghum flour, 5.48 g guar gum powder, 6.84 g moisture content of feed, 130 °C extruder barrel temperature, 350 rpm crew speed and 0.5 rpm feed rate resulting in 3.580 expansion ratio, 0.111 g/cm³ bulk density and 890.66 g hardness. Experimental values were found very close to the predicated values.

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